

Building a network

Case study from Sweden

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Background

Swedish Social Science Data Service (SSD)

- **Phase 1:** 1980-1985, project at the department for Political Science, University of Gothenburg, national research infrastructure covering social sciences, funded by project funds from the Swedish Research Council for Humanities and Social Sciences (HSFR)
- **Phase 2:** 1985-2005, unit at the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Gothenburg, national research infrastructure covering social sciences, funded through the university budget.
- **Phase 3:** 2006-2007, transferred to the Swedish Research Council (VR), hosted by University of Gothenburg, national research infrastructure covering social sciences, funded by the Research Council

Swedish National Data Service (SND)

- **Phase 4:** 2008-2017, established by the Swedish Research Council, hosted by University of Gothenburg, national research infrastructure covering social sciences, humanities and health science, from 2016 also covering environment & climate, 2/3 of the basic funding from the Research Council, 1/3 from the University of Gothenburg, 2 x 5 year funding periods

Organisation from 2018

- **Phase 5:** 2018-2022, consortium of 9 universities, main office hosted by University of Gothenburg, national research infrastructure covering all disciplines, 50% of the basic funding from the Research Council, 25% from University of Gothenburg and the rest (in kind) from the other consortium members.

The SND office, with support from the nine consortium universities, serves as a hub for the research data support functions (DAU) that are being established.

The Consortium

A collaboration between nine* universities that contribute with expertise from different scientific fields or domains.

*KTH-Royal Institute of Technology and Chalmers University of Technology joined the consortium in October 2019.

Each consortium university appoint a member to the SND Steering Group and to the annual meeting (deciding the budget)

University of Gothenburg
Humanities, social sciences,
public health/epidemiology

Lund University
Materials science,
environmental and climate data,
interdisciplinary population-based research

The domain specialists are experts in various scientific fields or in areas of research data management. They function as a bridge between groups of researchers and the research community at large, on the one hand, and between the data repository and the local DAU.

Umeå University
Register-based research

Uppsala University
Sensitive data

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Environmental and climate data

Stockholm University
Spatial data (geodata, GIS data),
environmental and climate data

Karolinska Institutet
Life sciences

The SND network

Mid Sweden University
Dalarna University
Örebro University
Karlstad University
University of Skövde
University West
University of Borås
University of Gothenburg
RISE
Chalmers University of Technology
Jönköping University
Halmstad University
Lund University
Malmö University

Luleå University of Technology
Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
Umeå University
University of Gävle
Uppsala University
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Mälardalen University
Stockholm University
Karolinska Institutet
KTH Royal Institute of Technology
Stockholm School of Economics
Swedish Defence University
Södertörn University
Linköping University
Linnaeus University
Kristianstad University
Blekinge Institute of Technology

Building & strengthening the Network

Most of the universities in the network submitted a Letter of Intent to the application for funding, some joined later. Each network member pays an annual fee of 75 000 SEK (approx. 7 500 €)

- The network members will operate independently in creating their local RDM functions, but can ask SND for support and advice.
- Progress toward the establishment of a DAU varies between the network member
- Each network member has a contact person at SND
- The network members are encouraged to participate in a number of working groups initiated by SND
- Network meetings 4 times a year

The composition of a Data Access Unit

The composition and the official name of the DAU differ between the universities.

Most often people from:

- University library
- University archive
- IT department
- Legal department
- Grants office

Training

BAS Online

SND has developed a basic web-based training for DAU staff, [BAS Online](#) (in Swedish only).

Research data: Accessibility, Management, and Collaboration

Training at the Swedish School of Library and Information Science in Borås (in collaboration with SND)

120 hours including 4 meetings in Borås. The third round of the training is currently underway and a fourth round is planned

Workflow Researcher – DAU - SND

Activities started in 2018

Strategic Plan 2018-2022 and Annual Plans

- My SND – Overview & status of data descriptions
 - Deposit form - Metadata adaption to 5 subject areas
 - DAU Handbook
 - Common national storage
-

Overview & status of data descriptions

To login use SWAMID (university ID) or sign in via facebook or google.

Researchers:

Overview & status of their own data descriptions

DAU:

Overview & status of the university's data descriptions

SND:

Overview & status of all data descriptions

The screenshot displays the SND (Swedish National Data Service) web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the SND logo and the text 'Swedish National Data Service'. To the right, there is a search bar and the text 'Search on site | På Svenska'. Below the navigation bar, there is a breadcrumb trail: 'Home / Data descriptions'. The main content area is titled 'Data descriptions' and features a '+ Create new' button. Below this, there is a 'Show' dropdown menu set to '10' and a 'Filter:' input field. A table with columns 'Title', 'Date', and 'Actions' is shown, but it is empty, displaying the message 'No data available in table'. At the bottom of the table, there are icons for home, list, print, and a 'Previous' / 'Next' navigation pair. On the right side, there is an 'Information' panel with a plus icon and the text: 'Click *Create new* to begin a new data description. Earlier data descriptions (submitted or not) are listed in the panel on the left. The status *Editing* indicates that the data description has not been submitted for review, and requires completion and data upload. Information from an existing data description can also be copied into a new data description. You will receive an email notification as soon as we begin reviewing your data description. You will also be contacted if more information is required before publication.'

Metadata adaption to 5 subject areas

Deposit form - The general metadata profile supplemented by five specific profiles

- Archaeology and history
- Earth and environmental sciences
- Language resources
- Medical and health sciences
- Social science

More information on depositing data can be found at <https://snd.gu.se/en/describe-and-share-data>

The screenshot shows the 'New data description' form on the SND website. The header includes the SND logo and the text 'Swedish National Data Service', along with a 'CORE TRUST SEAL' logo. The navigation menu contains links for 'Find and order data', 'Describe and deposit data', 'Data Management', 'SND events', 'About us', and 'Internat'. Below the navigation menu, there are additional links: 'Form to describe data', 'Terms and Conditions', 'How it works', 'Fördelar', 'FAQ', and 'How to describe research data'. The main content area shows the breadcrumb 'Home / Data descriptions / New data description' and the title 'New data description'. The form includes three main sections: 'Title (in swedish) *' with a text input field and a note 'Title of the study. If the study only has a Swedish title, use the Swedish title below too.'; 'Title (in english) *' with a text input field; and 'Data accessibility level *' with a sub-section 'Access to data through SND or other external actor *' containing two radio button options: 'Access to data through SND' and 'Access to data through an external actor'.

DAU Handbook

Wiki format with possibilities for the local DAU to add information

Resource to:

- fulfill the metadata and data requirements
- build own work routines around incoming data, processing, publication of data, and research contacts
- use available software / services
- create routines around contact with and support for researchers.

The first contents of the manual are developed in an internal project at SND in collaboration with a reference group from the DAU units in the network.

Common national storage

- Collaboration with SUNET (Swedish University Computer Network) and SNIC (Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing) on national storage solution for research data.
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Activities started in 2019

- Pilot study – Testing the metadata & data workflow
 - DORIS - Upgrading the deposit form
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Testing the metadata & data workflow

- A pilot project with eight network members
- Purpose: Testing the metadata & data data workflow
- The researcher describes and uploads data in the web form.
- A DAU representative reviews data and metadata.
- The DAU representative reports back to the researcher.
- The description is published in the research data catalogue.
- The data are given a DOI and stored.

DORIS

- Upgrading the deposit form. Possibility to edit data description after publishing

Activities planned for 2020

- Implementing the PID policy
- Roadmap for TDR certification of all parts of the network

Questions?

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SND

Svensk nationell datatjänst

| Göteborgs universitet - Karolinska Institutet - Lunds universitet - Stockholms universitet - Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet - Umeå universitet - Uppsala universitet